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Research Article

**DESIGN, CHARACTERIZATION AND *IN VITRO*
EVALUATION OF RIFAXIMIN EFFERVESCENT
FLOATING TABLETS****Katta Ashwini¹ K. Kishore² Dr. Gampa Vijay Kumar³**^{1,2,3}KGR Institute Of Technology And Management, Rampally, Kesara, Rangareddy,
Telangana, India.**Abstract:**

In the present research work effervescent floating formulation of Rifaximin by using various polymers. Initially analytical method development was done for the drug molecule. Absorption maxima was determined based on that calibration curve was developed by using different concentrations. Gas generating agent sodium bicarbonate was used. Then the formulation was developed by using different concentrations of polymers of various polymers. The formulation blend was subjected to various preformulation studies, flow properties and all the formulations were found to be good indicating that the powder blend has good flow properties. Among all the formulations the formulations prepared by using Guar gum produced maximum drug release compared to other formulations hence it was considered as the optimized formulation. The optimized formulation dissolution data was subjected to release kinetics, from the release kinetics data it was evident that the formulation followed zero order kinetics of drug release.

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INTRODUCTION:

Floating drug delivery systems (FDDS) have a bulk density less than gastric fluids and so remain buoyant in the stomach without affecting the gastric emptying rate for a prolonged period of time. While the system is floating on the gastric contents, the drug is released slowly at the desired rate from the system. After release of drug, the residual system is emptied from the stomach.

Non-Effervescent systems

These are also called as hydrodynamically balanced systems (HBS). They incorporate gel-forming or highly swellable cellulose type hydrocolloids, polysaccharides, and matrix forming polymers such as polycarbonate, polyacrylate, polymethacrylate and polystyrene. The buoyancy to these dosage forms is provided by air trapped in the swollen polymer. Sheth and Tossounian postulated that when such dosage forms come in contact with an aqueous medium, the hydrocolloid starts to hydrate by first forming a gel at the surface of the dosage form. This gel structure then regulates the rate of diffusion of solvent-in and drug-out of the dosage form. As the outer surface goes into solution, the gel barrier is maintained by the hydration of immediate adjacent hydrocolloid layer. As a result, the drug dissolves in and diffuses out with the diffusing solvent, creating a 'receding

boundary of the HBS.

Effervescent systems

A drug delivery system can be made to float in the stomach by incorporating a floating chamber, which may be filled with vacuum, air, or inert gas. The gas in floating chamber can be introduced either by volatilization of an organic solvent or by effervescent reaction between organic acids and bicarbonate salts.

Materials

Rifaximin is the sample from Natco Private Limited. PVP K 15, HPMC K 15M, Guar gum, Carbopol 934 P, Sodium Bicarbonate, Magnesium Stearate, Micro Crystalline Cellulose, Talc all the chemicals used were laboratory grade.

Method of Preparation**Optimization of Sodium bicarbonate concentration:**

Sodium bicarbonate was employed as effervescent gas generating agent. It helps the formulation to float. Various concentrations of sodium bicarbonate were employed; floating lag time and floating duration were observed. Based on that the concentration of sodium bicarbonate was finalized and preceded for further formulations.

Table 1. Optimization sodium bicarbonate concentration

S.No	Excipient Name	EF1	EF2	EF3
1	Rifaximin	200	200	200
2	Guar gum	50	50	50
4	NaHCO ₃	50	75	100
5	Mg.Stearate	5	5	5
5	Talc	5	5	5
7	MCC pH 102	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S
	Total weight	450	450	450

All the quantities were in mg.

The floating lag time of the EF1 is 70sec, EF2 is 40sec and EF3 is 90sec. Since EF2 has shown less time to float compared to EF1 & EF3. It is considered as the optimised concentration.

Table 2. Formulation composition for floating tablets

Formulation No.	Rifaximin	Sodium CMC	Chitosan	Guar gum	NaHCO ₃	Mag. Stearate	Talc	MCC pH 102
F1	200	50	-----	-----	75	5	5	QS
F2	200	75	-----	-----	75	5	5	QS
F3	200	100	-----	-----	75	5	5	QS
F4	200	-----	50	-----	75	5	5	QS
F5	200	-----	75	-----	75	5	5	QS
F6	200	-----	100	-----	75	5	5	QS
F7	200	-----	-----	50	75	5	5	QS
F8	200	-----	-----	75	75	5	5	QS
F9	200	-----	-----	100	75	5	5	QS

Evaluation of prepared tablets

The designed formulation tablets were studied for their physicochemical properties like weight variation, hardness, thickness, friability, Floating time, *In-vitro* release and drug content.

ResultsAnd Discussion

Standard graph of Rifaximin was taken in Simulated Gastric fluid (pH 1.2) at 244 nm.

Table 3: Observations for graph of Rifaximin in 0.1N HCl (244 nm)

concentration	Absorbance
0	0
0.1	0.131
0.2	0.274
0.3	0.394
0.4	0.547
0.5	0.682
0.6	0.844

Fig 1: Standard graph of Rifaximin in 0.1N HCl

Preformulation parameters of powder blend

The quality of tablet, once formulated by rule, is generally dictated by the quality of physicochemical properties of blends. There are many formulations and

process variables involved in mixing and all these can affect the characteristics of blends produced. The various characteristics of blends tested as per Pharmacopoeia.

Table 4:Pre-formulation parameters of blend

Formulation Code	Angle of Repose	Bulk density (gm/ml)	Tapped density (gm/ml)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's Ratio
F1	26.01	0.49	0.57	16.21	0.86
F2	24.8	0.56	0.62	16.87	0.98
F3	22.74	0.52	0.68	17.11	0.64
F4	25.33	0.54	0.64	17.67	1.12
F5	26.24	0.53	0.67	16.92	1.2
F6	26.12	0.56	0.66	17.65	1.06
F7	27.08	0.58	0.69	16.43	0.76
F8	25.12	0.48	0.57	17.97	1.15
F9	25.45	0.54	0.62	17.54	1.17

Quality Control Parameters For tablets

Tablet quality control tests such as weight variation, hardness, and friability, thickness, and drug release studies in different media were performed on the tablets

Table 5:Quality control parameters for tablets

Formulation code	Weight variation(mg)	Hardness(kg/cm ²)	Friability (%loss)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)	Floating lag time (min)
F1	452.5	3.5	0.52	3.1	99.76	4.0
F2	455.4	3.2	0.54	2.9	99.45	4.2
F3	448.6	3.4	0.51	2.9	99.34	4.5
F4	450.6	3.5	0.55	2.9	99.87	4.1
F5	449.4	3.4	0.56	2.7	99.14	4.0
F6	450.7	3.2	0.45	2.5	98.56	4.4
F7	452.3	3.1	0.51	2.4	98.42	4.5
F8	451.2	3.3	0.49	2.7	99.65	4.6
F9	448.3	3.5	0.55	2.6	99.12	4.7

In-Vitro Drug Release Studies**Table 6: Dissolution Data of Rifaximin Tablets**

Time(Hrs)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	3.77	9.14	5.12	6.75	8.11	5.18	3.11	10.37	15.38
1	10.51	16.76	12.45	12.34	14.5	11.81	7.15	21.11	27.77
2	18.4	25.77	17.47	24.88	20.82	21.27	14.21	31.55	36.44
3	24.15	29.42	23.42	31.55	26.89	25.43	27.54	35.68	43.77
4	32.13	34.64	29.18	38.76	34.14	37.51	35.45	39.77	47.59
5	37.91	41.32	36.71	42.44	41.67	43.14	45.21	43.28	49.85
6	42.92	49.12	41.78	45.89	47.64	47.15	53.77	47.77	54.66
7	48.18	54.77	48.89	48.59	58.66	51.79	59.34	49.86	64.01
8	54.32	58.74	52.22	53.55	63.77	53.14	66.73	52.37	75.77
9	59.93	64.4	58.42	59.87	76.52	63.18	77.69	56.61	77.55
10	64.82	77.31	63.34	62.09	83.76	68.14	85.54	62.44	79.55
11	69.77	85.12	69.42	74.66	88.15	74.19	91.15	69.55	84.65
12	78.22	89.21	77.47	78.55	94.36	83.45	97.05	75.33	87.54

Figure2: Dissolution Profiles Of Formulations F1-F9

Application of Release Rate Kinetics to Dissolution Data:

Table 7: Release kinetics data for optimised formulation (F10)

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	LOG (%) RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG (%) REMAIN
0	0	0			2.000
3.11	0.5	0.000	0.493	0.000	1.986
7.15	1	1.000	0.854	0.000	1.968
14.21	2	1.414	1.153	0.301	1.933
27.54	3	1.732	1.440	0.477	1.860
35.45	4	2.000	1.550	0.602	1.810
45.21	5	2.236	1.655	0.699	1.739
53.77	6	2.449	1.731	0.778	1.665
59.34	7	2.646	1.773	0.845	1.609
66.73	8	2.828	1.824	0.903	1.522
77.69	9	3.000	1.890	0.954	1.348
85.54	10	3.162	1.932	1.000	1.160
91.15	11	3.317	1.960	1.041	0.947
97.05	12	3.464	1.987	1.079	0.470

Figure 3: Zero order release kinetics graph

Figure 4:Higuchi release kinetics graph

Figure5: Karr's mayerspeppas graph

Figure 6: First order release kinetics graph

CONCLUSION:

The formulation blend was subjected to various preformulation studies, flow properties and all the formulations were found to be good indicating that the powder blend has good flow properties. Among all the formulations the formulation F7 prepared by using Guar gum 50mg produced maximum drug release compared to other formulations hence it was considered as the optimized formulation. The optimized formulation dissolution data was subjected to release kinetics, from the release kinetics data it was evident that the formulation followed zero order kinetics of drug release.

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